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The textile industry in Uzbekistan is the most important diversified and innovative-attractive sector of the economy, ensuring that the country maintains the status of an independent and sovereign industrial state, strengthening its defense capability, economic, social and intellectual security. It contributes to improving the life of the population, restoring and maintaining people's health, improving the ecology of the environment, solving the problems of socio-economic development of the regions of Uzbekistan.¹

Improving the welfare of the people is the main goal of the economic reforms set by the President of the Republic. The successful solution of this problem requires the solution of a wide range of socio-economic problems. It is known that in the production of the national economy, in various sectors and strata of society, in production, it is important to rationally organize and operate enterprises, strengthen the material and technical base, ensure the rational use of labor resources and manage them. one of the key questions.

The enterprise receives raw materials, energy, information, other resources and converts them into goods and services, profit, waste, etc. Open systems have, however, some specific features. One such feature is the recognition of the interdependence between the system and the external world. There is a boundary separating the system from its environment. Changes in the environment affect one or more attributes of the system, and conversely, changes in the system affect the environment.

Picture 1. Types of motivation LLC "OSIYO GRAND TEKSTIL"²

Promotion is a complex process. Certain requirements are imposed on the organization of this work. They mainly consist of:

Integrity means the separation of moral and material, social and personal incentives. Their importance depends on the approach to personnel management, the experience and traditions of the company or firm. The set also requires the presence of anti-stimuli.

Stratification refers to the individualization of different layers and groups of employees. It is well known that approaches to wealthy and low-income workers should differ significantly. Approaches to both experienced and young personnel should also be different.

Incentives for flexibility and agility imply regular review in response to changes in society and society.

Versatility. Employees should be able to qualify for every type of promotion. The terms of encouragement should be democratic and understandable for everyone.

Weight. Practice shows that incentives have a certain level of impact. This level varies from country to country and from community to community. For some employees, the 5,000 UZS reward is significant, while for others, the 50,000 UZS reward may not be enough. This feature should be taken into account when determining the lower level of incentives.

Step by step. The amount of financial incentives should be taken into account in practice. Providing a large amount of reward at one time gives hope that the amount of the next incentive for employees will be no less than this large reward. If this expectation is not met, the interest of employees will decrease. Therefore, no matter how high the level of stimulation, it is not

² Abramov V.S. Strategic management in 2 hours. Part 2. Functional strategies: textbook and workshop for universities / VS Abramov, SV Abramov; edited by V. S. Abramov. - Moscow: Yurayt Publishing House, 2021. - 246 p.

advisable to reduce it. Practical research shows that there is a linear relationship between the desired and actual level of incentives. As the reward amount increases, in many cases more rewards are expected for the same work.

The change between the result of labor and the wages paid for it; reduce as much as possible. The fact that most foreign firms pay weekly wages is primarily due to the fact that they follow the same principle. The effectiveness of the immediate introduction of incentives has long been known. Experiments have shown that adhering to this principle can even reduce rewards.

A combination of methods of material and spiritual stimulation. Both of these types of incentives have a big impact. Their use should take into account the level of development of the economy, traditions, the financial situation of the employee, age and gender. For example, if the employee is young, financial incentives are more effective.³

However, this does not mean that the use of spiritual stimulation is ineffective.

According to scientists, in a stable state of the economy, when a worker reaches the age of 50, material and moral incentives are almost equally important for him. Insufficient attention or overestimation of factors and types of incentives is detrimental to effective management in the enterprise.

When a person starts working, he has certain values and principles that he learned from his youth, and family and school are at the core of them. During this period, the attitude to work as a value begins to form, the labor qualities of a person - diligence, responsibility, discipline, initiative and other qualities. At the same time, initial working skills are formed.

To form an interest in work, it is extremely important to master these labor standards and values. Directly the same norms and values determine the content of future work activity, lifestyle. The potential for curiosity is crucial in the generality of these human abilities and abilities. It is this potential of interest that determines how the employee develops himself and

³ 3. Akmaeva R.I. Strategic management: textbook / R.I. Akmaeva - Moscow: Rusines, 2020. - 256 p.

how effectively he can use the available opportunities in the work process.⁴

Motivation is the most important factor in labor efficiency and, as a basis, underlies the labor potential of an employee.

Labor potential consists of psychophysiological potential (abilities and interests of a person, state of health, ability to work, endurance, type of nervous system) and personal (interesting) potential. The potential for curiosity is crucial in the generality of these human abilities and abilities. It is this potential of interest that determines how the employee develops himself and how effectively he can use the available opportunities in the work process.

The legal framework for the relationship between a manager and a leader plays an important role in increasing labor activity. This basis gives the employee the right to independently choose the method of carrying out the labor process within the framework of clearly defined legal norms.

As an employee is promoted, his or her profit partnership will increase by one-third, as defined. Companies and firms will also have a personal reward system for employees. According to him, in some cases financial assistance is provided at the request of an employee or at the initiative of the administration.

In enterprises, the remuneration system is currently divided into two levels: the annual remuneration system and the monthly remuneration system. The annual bonus system is based on the end of the year and is commonly referred to as the "thirteenth salary". The monthly bonus system consists of various forms and methods of the employee incentive system.

Remuneration for the performance of individual tasks is paid from the wage fund for the number of days actually worked by the employee in the current month.

Another type of incentive is the provision of preferential (interest-free) loans to employees. Many companies and firms also have the practice of providing material assistance in the amount of 5 to 10 minimum wages in connection with the birth of a child, marriage (marriage registration), death of close relatives.

⁴ Abramov V.S. Strategic management in 2 hours. Part 2. Functional strategies: textbook and workshop for universities / VS Abramov, SV Abramov; edited by V. S. Abramov. - Moscow: Yurayt Publishing House, 2021. - 246 p.

Economic methods are the most common interest rate method. These methods lie directly (wages, bonuses, additional payments) and indirectly (benefits: food, paid vacation, life and health insurance, pensions and incentives). Many companies try to tie the employee's salary to the results of work in the current period. At the same time, market principles should be taken into account: the subsistence minimum, labor supply, the level of wages paid by competitors, the harmonization of wages by the state, etc.

Reference

1. Abramov V.S. Strategic management in 2 hours. Part 2. Functional strategies: textbook and workshop for universities / VS Abramov, SV Abramov; edited by V. S. Abramov. - Moscow: Yurayt Publishing House, 2021. - 246 p.
2. Agafonov V.A. Strategic management. Models and procedures: monograph/ V.A. Agafonov. - Moscow: INFRA-M, 2018. - 276 p.
3. Akmaeva R.I. Strategic management: textbook / R.I. Akmaeva - Moscow: Rusines, 2020. - 256 p.
4. <https://bank.nauchniestati.ru/primery/referat-na-temu-upravlenie-personalom-v-sisteme-menedzhmenta-organizacii/>
5. <https://www.vedomosti.ru/management/articles/2014/12/02/kadry-ne-dolzhen-melkat>